

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-132-IBN-5-10% 05 RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	16	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 132
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	286.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 286.0 nm (2998
Date Acquired:	3/4/2023 8:26:44 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 4:13:42 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.388	3965876	20.81	361464
2	10.720	5853125	30.72	484855
3	11.403	5553877	29.15	428455
4	12.101	3680302	19.32	267722

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-87-IBN-5-10% 05 ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230306
Vial:	2	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 288
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	286.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 286.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/6/2023 6:13:58 PM CST		
Date Processed:	7/4/2023 8:16:28 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.295	1593844	3.33	136859
2	10.634	192629	0.40	22142
3	11.228	45749664	95.62	2941385
4	11.936	309945	0.65	18518